

Supplementary information (SI) for:

Evaluating net-GWP Benefits of mycelium-based composites in traditional timber frame construction systems

Dana Sàez¹, Dóra Márfoldi² and Martin Trautz¹

¹ Chair for structures and structural design, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

² Marcell Breuer Doctoral School of Architecture, University of Pécs, Hungary

E-mail: saez@trako.arch.rwth-aachen.de

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1. Life cycle inventory Analysis (LCI)

1.1. Data collection

Life cycle inventory Analysis (LCI) represents the life cycle inventory flows per functional unit (1 m³ MBC, 1 m² TFCMBC) considered in the LCA.

Table 1. LCI flows per functional unit.

life-cycle stage	flows	amount for 1 m ³ MBC	amount for 1 m ² TFCMBC	unit	source of amount	source process
A1	agar-agar	7.50E-03	1.20E-03	kg	primary, according to lab protocol	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	spruce wood chips	1.99E+02	3.19E+01	kg	primary, according to lab protocol	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	wheat bran	9.97E+01	1.60E+01	kg	primary, according to lab protocol	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	deionized water	2.44E+02	3.91E+01	kg	primary, according to lab protocol	Ecoinvent 3.10
A2	transport	9.23E+05	4.55E+04	kg*km	primary, according to own calculations	Ecoinvent 3.10
A3	surface disinfectant	3.36E+00	5.37E-01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	disposable gloves	6.64E-02	1.06E-02	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	polystyrene (disposable Petri dish)	1.57E-02	2.51E-03	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	paper (paper towel)	7.59E-01	1.21E-01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	deionised water	7.39E+01	1.18E+01	kg	primary, according to lab protocol	Ecoinvent 3.10
	paraffin foil	2.96E+00	4.73E-01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	polypropilene autoclavable bags	8.97E+00	1.43E+00	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	plywood	6.34E-01	1.01E-01	m ³	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	phenol	2.88E+00	4.61E-01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	electricity consumption	5.87E+03	1.04E+03	kWh	secondary, according to the user manual information of the equipments	Ecoinvent 3.10

A3	waste rubber	6.64E-02	1.06E-02	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	waste treatment, polystyrene	1.57E-02	1.57E-02	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	disposal, common waste	3.15E-01	9.107E-01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	waste treatment, polypropylene	8.97E+00	1.43E+00	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	waste water treatment	7.39E+01	1.89E+01	kg	secondary, according to the user manual information of the autoclave	Ecoinvent 3.10
C2	transport	2.49E+04	5.37E+03	kg*km	primary, according to own calculations	Ecoinvent 3.10
C3	grinding	2.49E+02	80.73	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Agribalyse 3.3.1
	waste timber	-	4.09E+01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	Ecoinvent 3.10
	waste MBC	2.49E+02	3.99E+01	kg	primary, according to own measurements	internal process

1.2. LCI results

The collected data was calculated using the OpenLCA 2.2.0 software, utilizing the EN15804+A2 life cycle impact assessment method. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the contribution of the assessed life cycle stages to the total net-GWP assessment with module D_MBCp.

Figure 1. net-GWP contribution, 1 m³ MBC core material.

Figure 2. net-GWP contribution within the life cycle, 1 m² TFCMBC.

2. Data sensitivity assessment

2.1. Data quality entry

The data quality entry was elaborated for all the collected data according to the Pedigree matrix (1) and covers the flows of both production systems (MBC, TFCMBC).

flow	reliability	completeness	temporal colleration	georgraphical correlation	further technological correlation
spruce softwood	1	1	1	1	1
agar agar	1	1	1	3	1
waste timber	1	1	1	2	2
water, deionised	1	1	1	1	1
wheat bran	1	1	1	2	1
sawmill leftover	1	1	1	3	1
transport	1	1	1	1	1
polypropylene bag production	1	2	1	3	2
electricity, low voltage, renewable energy products	1	1	1	1	2
rubber gloves	1	1	1	2	3
isopropanol	1	1	1	2	1
paraffin	1	2	1	2	1
phenol	1	3	1	2	5
plywood production	1	1	1	2	1
polystyrene, general purpose	1	1	1	2	1
residual wood, dry	1	2	1	2	5
paper towel	1	1	1	2	1
sawnwood, lath, hardwood, raw, dried production	1	1	1	2	1
structural timber production	1	1	1	2	1
disposal, common waste	1	1	1	3	1
waste prolypropylene	1	1	1	2	1
waste rubber	1	1	1	2	1
waste water treatment	1	1	1	2	1
grinding	1	1	1	3	2
waste MBC	1	1	1	1	1
municipal waste incineration for heat recovery	1	1	1	2	1
waste timber	1	1	1	2	2
particle board production	1	1	1	2	1
soil	1	1	1	1	1

2.2. Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis was performed with the Monte Carlo simulation tool integrated in OpenLCA 2.2.0, using the Pedigree matrix data quality metrics. The standard deviation results were averaged over the evaluated life cycle stages and plotted in a graph (Figure 3). The highest levels of uncertainty were observed in phase A3 and module D, due to the significant number of flows associated with these stages. Furthermore, the data sources used in this study, namely Ecoinvent and Agribalyse, do not always cover regional specific conditions and flows, contributing to the increase in uncertainty. This limitation highlights the need for further assessment and refinement in future research.

Figure 3. Result of the sensitivity analysis. Standard deviation.

The contribution to the uncertainties was calculated based on the standard deviation values and summarized in . The main contributors are marked in bold.

Table 2. Contribution to the variance by uncertainties.

flows	net-GWP	GWP _{bio}	GWP _{fossil}	GWP _{luluc}
agar agar production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
wheat bran production	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
spruce softwood	0.018	0.001	0.000	0.560
sawmill leftover	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
transport freight, lorry	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
polypropylene bag production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
electricity consumption	0.958	0.815	0.983	0.426
isopropanol production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
paraffin production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
rubber gloves	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
lath, softwood production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
sawing and planing	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.007

structural timber production	0.000	0.011	0.000	0.000
phenol production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
plywood production	0.000	0.061	0.016	0.007
polystyrene production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
paper towel	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
deionised water production	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
disposal, common waste	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
waste polypropylene treatment	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
waste rubber	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
waste water treatment	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
grinding	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
waste MBC	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
municipial incineration	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
waste timber framework	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
particle board production	0.021	0.000	0.000	0.000

3. Reference service life

The MBC core material is compared with eight conventional core materials (Figure 4), and the TFCMBC is compared with two commercial sandwich structures (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Comparison of 1 m³ MBC with eight conventional core materials.

Figure 5. Comparison of 1 m² TFCMBC with two conventional sandwich structures.

4. References

1. Ciroth A, Muller S, Weidema B, Lesage P. Empirically based uncertainty factors for the pedigree matrix in ecoinvent. *Int J Life Cycle Assess.* 2016 Sep;21(9):1338–48.